

COMMUNICATIVE-PRAGMATIC COMPETENCE AS AN EFFECTIVE SOURCE FOR ACADEMIC WRITING IN PROFICIENCY TESTS

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Annotation. This article discusses didactic and communicative approaches, beliefs and techniques of assessing communicative-pragmatic competence of English proficiency test takers as well as English practitioners or users. Pragmatic competence within communicative conditions is regarded as a source of testing and assessing student or test taker's linguistic and communicative abilities reflected through academic writing tasks. Techniques for measuring academic writing and pragmatic ability are suggested through reflecting a series of testing tools, approaches and didactic activities relying on comprehensive past and current research studies, technologies and practices in foreign and second language assessment.

Key words: evaluation, assessment, testing, objective, proficiency, academic writing, EFL, ESL, TOEFL, norm-referencing, criterion, pragmatic skills, speech act, authentic, real-world, examination, approach, technique, specialist, qualification, competence, ability, foreign and second language, level, English for Academic Purposes, students

INTRODUCTION

Marking is one of the most complicated tasks that EFL, EAL and ESL teachers are required to perform. Correcting students' mistakes and giving students a mark is merely the tip of the iceberg when we talk about overall assessment and evaluation.

Research from studies and practices in language assessment reviews the differences between assessment and evaluation in the ESL classroom, and offers advice

to help tackle the challenging task of assessing skills. When English teachers assess students' progress, they first need to check on the lesson objectives. Then the teacher needs to come up with a method for checking that their students have achieved the proficiency level that was expected of them.

A good assessment should inform the teacher if the ESL lesson was effective and how it can be improved. It should also be the base for further planning since new concepts should not be taught until the students have achieved the objectives.

MAIN BODY

When we are talking about giving people a test and recording scores etc., we would normally refer to this as an assessment procedure.

If, on the other hand, we are talking about looking back over a course or a lesson and deciding what went well, what was learnt and how people responded, we would prefer the term 'evaluate' as it seems to describe a wider variety of data input (testing, but also talking to people and recording impressions and so on). Evaluation does not have to be very elaborate. The term could be used to describe nodding to accept an answer in class up to formal examinations set by international testing bodies but at that end of the cline, we are more likely to talk about assessment and examining.

Another difference in use is that when we measure success for ourselves (as in teaching a lesson) we are conducting evaluation; when someone else does it, it is called assessment.

Formative testing is used to enhance and adapt the learning program. Such tests help both teachers and learners to see what has been learned and how well and to help set targets. It has been called educational testing. Formative evaluation may refer to adjusting the program or helping people see where they are.

In other words, it may targeted at teaching or learning (or both). Summative tests, on the other hand, seek to measure how well a set of learning objectives has been achieved at the end of a period of instruction. Robert Stake describes the difference this way: When the cook tastes the soup, that's formative. When the guests taste the soup, that's summative. (cited in Scrivener, 1991:169).

Objective assessment (or, more usually, testing) is characterized by tasks in which there is only one right answer. It may be a multiple-choice test, a True/False test or any other kind of test where the result can readily be seen and is not subject to the marker's judgment. Subjective tests are those in which questions are open ended and the marker's judgment is important. Of course, there are various levels of test on the subjective-objective scale.

Criterion-referenced tests are those in which the result is measured against a scale (e.g., by grades from A to E or by a score out of 100, for example, CEFR assessment or test-rater on knowledge and skills, proficiency test rater scale A1-C2, rubric, benchmark). The object is to judge how well someone did against a set of objective criteria independently of any other factors.

A good example is a driving test. Norm-referencing is a way of measuring students against each other. For example, if 10% of a class are going to enter the next class up, a norm-referenced test will not judge how well they achieved a task in a test but how well they did against the other students in the group. Some universities apply norm-referencing tests to select undergraduates.

At the height of the structural approach to language teaching there was a period when objective techniques specially transformations (Allen & Widdowson, 1978) and multiple choice, dominated language testing. This domination is evident, for example, in the TOEFL (Test of English as a Foreign Language, Educational Testing Service, New Jersey), which was first devised in the late 1960s and which consists of entirely of multiple-choice questions testing listening, reading, grammar and vocabulary. In recent years, this domination has been revised as second-generation testing has given way to third-generation. Third-generation tests generally include a broader mix of objective and subjective items, with less reliance on multiple-choice questions. Third-generation tests are referred to as communicative testing.

The shortcomings of objective testing have become more evident as the shortcomings of subjective testing have been reduced. The first shortcoming of early objective items, especially multiple-choice was their discrete-point nature, which was

overcome to a certain extent by the development of cloze and other integrative items. It is often said that multiple-choice testing encourages guessing, as, if there are four options there is a probability of achieving simply by choosing the same option for each question.

Objective items offer very real advantages to the tester. These advantages derive from their objectivity – they are easy to score, quick to score and, in theory, totally reliable. Their disadvantage as testing devices derives from their receptive nature – they cannot test productive language in any useful or meaningful way, and it is precisely these language areas, which are felt to be the most important in today’s world.

As subjective testing is targeted at measuring test taker’s and student’s communicative abilities, it gives wide access to identifying student’s academic abilities in writing a note, essay, completing academic paper, report, review, analytical report, descriptive or evaluative paper and other. Apart from language items – grammar (part of speech, word order, punctuation, spelling; vocabulary (word spelling and meaning), communicative tests or integrative tests assess student’s ability to use language and necessary academic skills in context (given task situation) and allow construction of flexible relation between the writer/student performing the written task and the task or assignment being evaluated.

In terms of evaluation, like in standard tests, TOEFL or IELTS academic, subjective testing based on normally accepted, well-developed assessment and evaluation criterion is frequently offered and employed. These techniques are often reflected in proficiency exams and classroom academic writing course assessment procedures. While attempting to place or use correct structures, words or phrases to fill the gap, to respond to the question in accurate writing manner, a student has to pass through several steps for communication with the test in terms of task comprehension, topic understanding, knowledge restoration, repetition, revision, word or paragraph selection and sentence appropriacy-matching, structuring paragraphs throughout the text or essay, deciding and structuring appropriate lines in writing proper introduction, body and conclusion, drafting and improving-error correction, matching linguistic and

pragmatic within communicative purpose with context (task situation) and content, relevance of writing manner and product in terms of pragmatic skills reflected in Grice’s maxims and use of relevant and effective speech acts, expression of proper pragmatic knowledge and ability (pragmatic intention, writer audience, author-task-writer relation/attitude, purpose, message, tone, register-formal, informal, comprehension (perlocutionary act), specific word order or words appropriate to context, and performance), within illocutionary acts for performance (speech acts: constative-assertive – he tells, he states, he concludes, constative-descriptive –he describes, he presents, directive-he questions, he requests that, he asks, he advises that, etc; commissive –he offers, he promises, etc; expressive-acknowledgement -he apologizes, he condolences, he congratulates), discourse management in the light of ability to understand and use appropriate discourse markers, connectors to build cohesion between sentences, coherence-overall meaningful text, correct signposting, words–synonyms, antonyms to show relations between expressed notions, reference markers- relevant pronouns, demonstratives, substitution and ellipsis and other discursive-communicative functions.

Having considered these and other communicative and sub-functional-pragmatic features of academic writing test tasks and essential relations between the test /task items and test taker or student, current academic proficiency tests, TOEFL, IELTS Academic, iTEP-Academic Plus and other university-level, graduate and undergraduate academic English tests frequently rely on communicative testing principles and methods to provide subjective but effectively communication-conscious testing reflecting high levels of authenticity – authentic tasks reflecting native-like atmosphere as if students or test takers perform in the real-world, in their context, real academic tasks using adequate or proficient English. This allows more authenticity in tasks and motivation to feel real world experience though most tasks imitate performance in EFL learning and testing settings.

As for the discussion of use of proficiency tests in higher educational contexts, it should be noted that unlike achievement tests, proficiency tests do not look back over

the syllabus taught in the past rather they look forward to a future language-using situation. They are usually related to a specific academic and/or occupational area where English is needed, for example, being a teacher or a nurse. The proficiency test then assesses whether the student has not only the appropriate level of English, but also the appropriate type of English. Proficiency tests, therefore, tend to have an EPP, ESP (English for Professional Purposes, English for Specific Purposes) flavor because they include language which is relevant to the language-using situation. So, test for teacher or nurse will have to include both English for Academic Purposes (EAP), such as reading textbooks, listening to lectures, writing assignments and speaking in seminars and English for Occupational Purposes (EOP), such as reading notes, listening to instructions on student/ patients' treatment, writing duty reports and speaking to students/colleagues or speaking to doctors and patients.

Hyland (2006) has claimed that pragmatic and critical perspectives on EAP is a central issue). In the last two decades, the field of EAP has witnessed a rising number of debates between advocates of pragmatic EAP and critical EAP in various contexts such as L2 writing, pedagogies and needs analysis. One of the early debates began after Santos (1992) claimed that L2 writing should be characterized by pragmatism and should not be ideological and political. She feels that it is easier and less problematic to be political at the local level (L1 writing), but not at the international level (L2 writing).

Pragmatism is the mainstream movement or approach in EAP, applied linguistics and L2 writing (Canagarajah, 2002; Santos, 2001). Santos (1992) asserts that by taking the pragmatic stance, the pedagogic approach to ESL writing especially in EAP should focus on preparing students to write their assignments. She adds that “pursuing political goals and/or changing students’ sociopolitical consciousness is not on the ESL writing agenda” (p. 9). Pragmatic EAP assumes that “students should accommodate themselves to the demands of academic assignments, behaviors expected in academic classes, and hierarchical arrangements within academic institutions” (Benesch, 2001a, p. 41). In a pragmatic approach to EAP, students are assisted to “fit unquestioningly

into subordinate roles in their disciplines and courses” (Hyland, 2006, p. 30). Teachers take an active role to decide basically on everything about a course – the syllabus, the students’ tasks and the content delivery. Hyland adds that one of the main objectives of this approach is “to empower learners by initiating them into the ways of making meanings that are valued in their target courses and disciplines” (p. 31). Developing learners’ academic communicative competence is also emphasized in this approach. Nonetheless, the fact that teachers are the ones playing an active role compared to students may be seen as limiting the students from exploring their full role as learners.

Many companies, government bodies and educational institutions have their own internal proficiency tests which relate to their own situation, so that the chocolate makers, Cadburys, have one for factory workers whose mother tongue is not English. Others are available as public examinations. The NEAB’s University Entrance Test in ESOL and the UCLES/ British Council International IELTS are both examples of EAP tests which are widely used by universities, while the ICC’s Certificate in English for the Hotel and Catering Industry is an example of an EOP examination (Davies & West).

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, proficiency tests are usually large-scale tests because important academic and career decisions are made as a result of them. In many cases, these are used as selection tests and the acceptance or rejection of applicants is based; in part, on their results. Alternatively, they may form part of their qualification, so that specialists have to pass their English proficiency test before they can graduate. So, reliable, well-constructed, technique-based and accurate rater-using communicative proficiency tests assessing and evaluating students’ linguistic abilities along with pragmatic skills peculiar to academic study and work, will allow English language, EPP and ESP learners to experience and evaluate their original written or related language performance through an authentic test or examination operations as proof of their readiness and response to complete real world tasks.

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